

Whole-genome sequencing of two promising *Bacillus thuringiensis* strains selected for their potential in the biocontrol of phytopathogenic fungi and insects

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Abstract

This study reveals the complete genome sequences obtained through whole-genome shotgun sequencing (WGS) of two *Bacillus* strains, isolated from different origins (Tunisia and Lebanon) and selected for the biocontrol of phytopathogen fungi and Lepidopteran insects. Based on the MLST classification, the BUPM14 (isolated from Tunisian soil) and BUPM255 strains (isolated from Lebanese soil), were identified as members of the *Bacillus cereus* group, and more specifically, *B. thuringiensis* strains. Previous analyses of these two strains revealed the production of secondary metabolites that likely play a crucial role in fighting phytopathogens. WGS is used as a more efficient and reliable approach to provide greater insights into the biocontrol mechanisms of these two *Bacillus thuringiensis* strains.

Introduction

Biological control using biopesticides is a safe alternative strategy to reduce the use of chemicals thus contributing to environmental preservation (Pretty, 2008). Microbial pesticides are the most popular (Pathak *et al.*, 2017), and the available ones belong mostly to the *Bacillus* genus. *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt) is the entomopathogenic bacterium belonging to the *Bacillus* genus which has been successfully applied against several phytopathogens with differences in potency and specificity (Crickmore, 2000). Bt-based formulations are the most used biopesticides worldwide and represent almost 90 % of the world's biopesticide market (Jallouli *et al.*, 2021). They are of overarching importance since they target different insect orders such as Diptera, Coleoptera, Hymenoptera, and Mallophaga (Melo *et al.*, 2016). Thus, Bt strains are classified into six pathotypes based on their range of insecticidal activity (Rao *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, the number and the diversity of metabolites produced by different Bt strains drawn in its virulence were broadly reported. In addition to Cry toxins which are the major toxins responsible for insecticidal activity, Bt produces Vip toxins (Andrés-Garrido *et al.*, 2020), Sip toxins (Kumar *et al.*, 2021), exoenzymes (chitinases, proteases, β -glucanases...) (Driss *et al.*, 2005), lipopeptides (Hathout *et al.*, 2000), parasorins (Girija *et al.*, 2023), bacteriocins (Kamoun *et al.*, 2011) ...

In our previous work, BUPM14 and BUPM255 strains were shown to be endowed with insecticidal and antifungal activities. The initial analyses revealed the production of different Cry toxins, and secondary metabolites that are involved in the target fungal suppression process (unpublished; Driss *et al.*, 2005). In the current study, we present the WGS of these two strains. The WGS is used as a more efficient and reliable approach to shed light on the molecular and operational mechanisms underlying the effectiveness of these bacteria through the comprehension of their biocontrol mechanisms.

Material and Methods

Bacterial isolates

BUPM255 and BUPM14 are soil-isolated strains from Lebanese and Tunisian samples, respectively, taken from the rhizosphere of olive trees (Driss *et al.*, 2005; 2015). They belong to the bacterial collection of the Laboratory of Biopesticides at the Centre of Biotechnology of Sfax (Tunisia). They were selected among a collection of isolates sampled and tested for their antagonist activity towards *Aspergillus niger*. Strains were grown at 30 °C using LB medium (Driss *et al.*, 2005).

Sequencing of bacterial genomic DNA

The genomic DNA sequences from the isolates were acquired by a sequencing service provider named MicrobesNG (Birmingham, UK; <https://microbesng.com>). Genomic DNA libraries were prepared using the Nextera XT Library Prep Kit (Illumina, San Diego, USA) following the manufacturer's protocol with the following modifications: input DNA was increased 2-fold, and PCR elongation time was increased to 45 seconds. DNA quantification and library preparation were carried out on a Hamilton Microlab STAR automated liquid handling system (Hamilton Bonaduz AG, Switzerland). Libraries were sequenced on an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 sequencer (Illumina, San Diego, USA) using a 250 bp paired-end protocol. Adapters were trimmed from reads using Trimmomatic version 0.30 (Bolger *et al.*, 2014) with a sliding window quality cutoff of Q15. *De novo* assembly was performed using SPAdes version 3.7 (Bankevich *et al.*, 2012), and contigs were annotated using Prokka 1.11 (Seemann, 2014).

Taxonomic nomenclature

The Average Nucleotide Identity (ANI) calculator (Yoon *et al.*, 2017) was used to classify and

identify the two bacterial strains through the calculation of the OrthoANIu percentage between each strain and the *Bacillus thuringiensis* serovar *berliner* ATCC 10792 (*Bacillus thuringiensis* reference genome: ASM16161v1; RefSeq: GCF_000161615.1), a member of the *Bacillus cereus* group. It was also used to compare both strains to each other. The taxonomic nomenclature was confirmed using the PubMLST.org website (Jolley *et al.*, 2018).

Results

Data availability

The whole-genome shotguns for BUPM14 and BUPM255 have been deposited at DDBJ/ENA/GenBank under accession numbers JAXAWU000000000 and JAXAWV000000000, respectively. The versions described in this paper are JAXAWU010000000 and JAXAWV010000000, respectively.

Raw sequence reads have been deposited in the NCBI Sequence Read Archive under BioProject numbers PRJNA1043042 and PRJNA1043062 and run numbers SRR26886703 and SRR26887045 for BUPM14 and BUPM255, respectively.

Genomic Features

A summary of the genomic features for BUPM14 and BUPM255 is listed in Table 1. The assembling of sequence reads resulted in 182 contigs for both strains. The cumulative contig lengths of the genome assemblies are 6.4 Mb with a mean coverage of more than 102X and 68X for BUPM14 and BUPM255, respectively. Other genomic features are similar for both strains. The number of protein-coding genes for BUPM14 is 6530 which is similar to that of BUPM255 (6564 genes). Both strains have almost equal genomic GC contents (34.73 % and 34.71 %, respectively) and tRNA (107 and 111, respectively), and equal numbers of tmRNA (1) and CRISPR (2).

Taxonomic classification

The taxon identification as *Bacillus thuringiensis* strains is based on the ANI values of 96.21 % and 96.20 % obtained for BUPM14 and BUPM255, respectively. This result was confirmed by the MLST taxonomic nomenclature (Table 2a). A sequence identity of 100 % was found between the submitted genomes of both strains and that of the *Bacillus thuringiensis* reference strain. The matching profile given by the Ribosomal MLST test (Table 2b) showed the membership of the two bacterial strains to the species *thuringiensis*. An ANI test was conducted to assess the relationship between both strains. The percentage of OrthoANIu value was 99.97 %, showing that both strains are strongly related, which is in perfect accordance with the similarities found for the genomic features.

Statement on continuing work

The datasets are being shared before formal publication and should be considered preliminary. We encourage and welcome feedback from the community. Please get in touch with Dr. Fatma Driss (fatma.driss@gmail.com) for more information.

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Table 1: Genomic features of the *Bacillus thuringiensis* BUPM14 and BUPM255 sequenced using Illumina.

Bacterial strain	Number of reads	Contigs (≥ 1 kb)	Largest contig (bp)	Total length (bp)	GC (%)	Mean coverage	N50 (bp)	CDS	tRNA	tmRNA	CRISPR	Bioproject	Biosample	GenBank accession (reads)	GenBank accession (assembly)
<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i> BUPM14	1359638	182	232069	6409205	34.73	102.053	96993	6530	107	1	2	PRJNA1043 042	SAMN3832 8827	SRR26886 703	JAXAWU00 0000000
<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i> BUPM255	919356	182	223560	6447512	34.71	68.8436	96993	6564	111	1	2	PRJNA1043 062	SAMN3832 9715	SRR26887 045	JAXAWV00 0000000

Table 2: MLST taxonomic nomenclature of BUPM14 and BUPM255. a) Predicted taxa; b) Ribosomal MLST (Matching profile).

	Rank	Taxon	Support	Taxonomy
a)	GENUS	<i>Bacillus</i>	100%	<i>Bacillota > Bacilli > Bacillales > Bacillaceae > Bacillus</i>

b)	rST	17172
	Genus	<i>Bacillus</i>
	Species	<i>Bacillus cereus/thuringiensis</i>